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LENDING TO MICROENTERPRISES IN UKRAINE: CURRENT STATE, PROBLEMS AND SOLUTION

JEL Classification: G21

SECTION “ECONOMICS”: Економіка

Annotation. The article identifies lending as one of the key ways for small and micro businesses to attract borrowed funds. It has been found that in today's conditions, the need to support and develop domestic small businesses has become even more relevant, since the collapse of large enterprises poses a threat to the security of the domestic economy, and the creation of a favorable climate for economic recovery, even in conditions of loss, is a consequence of support for small businesses. The relevance of this topic is determined by the need to solve a significant list of problems and eliminate obstacles to obtaining loans to ensure the normal functioning of micro businesses. The article establishes the essence and problems of financial support for micro businesses in Ukraine and proves that, in the current economic conditions; micro and small businesses are the driving force of the Ukrainian economy and, to this end and the foundations of a system for their financial support have already been laid. An analysis of the dynamics of non-performing loans was carried out and it was found that since the beginning of the full-scale invasion by the Russian Federation, the share of non-performing loans in Ukraine has begun to grow significantly. These circumstances have led to the risk of loan defaults and problems with the repayment of funds, which are caused by economic and organizational factors. The article examines the dynamics of non-performing loans in the period 2018-2024 and concludes that with the start of the war in Ukraine, the share of non-performing loans has grown rapidly, confirming the increased risk of loan defaults, as well as problems with loan repayment caused not only by economic but also by organizational factors. Particular attention is focused on the “Affordable Loans 5-7-9%” preferential loan program, which has become the main instrument of financial support for small businesses in Ukraine. The article examines the prerequisites for the emergence of alternative financing, which are summarized by a group of technological and economic factors. The article identifies and analyzes the main advantages of peer-to-peer lending compared to bank lending, including: greater accessibility and speed of obtaining a loan; reduced importance of credit ratings; financial support for socially significant projects; higher returns for investors, etc.

Keywords: lending, microenterprises, small businesses, alternative business financing, local budget, budget, taxes.

Анотація. У статті визначено, що одним із ключових способів залучення позикових ресурсів малим та мікробізнесом є його кредитування. Виявлено, що в умовах сьогодення

потреба підтримки та розвитку вітчизняного малого бізнесу стала ще актуальнішою, адже руйнування великих підприємств несе загрозу безпеці вітчизняній економіці, а створення сприятливого клімату для відновлення економіки навіть в умовах втрат є наслідком підтримки малого бізнесу. Актуальність даної теми визначена необхідністю вирішення значного переліку проблем та ліквідації перешкод на шляху отримання кредиту для забезпечення нормального рівня функціонування мікробізнесу. У статті встановлено сутність та проблеми фінансового забезпечення мікробізнесу в Україні, та доведено, що в сучасних умовах господарювання мікро- та малого бізнесу є двигуном української економіки і з цією метою вже закладено основи системи його фінансового забезпечення. Здійснено аналіз динаміки непрацюючих кредитів та виявлено, що від початку повномасштабного вторгнення РФ, в Україні частка непрацюючих кредитів почала суттєво зростати. Зазначені обставини призвели до ризику неповернення кредитів та проблем із поверненням коштів, що зумовлені економічними та організаційними факторами.

У статті досліджено динаміку непрацюючих кредитів у період 2018-2024 рр. та сформовано висновок, що з початком війни в Україні частка непрацюючих кредитів стрімко зросла, що підтверджує зростання ризику неповернення кредитів, а також проблеми із поверненням коштів, зумовлені не лише економічними, але й організаційними чинниками. Окрему увагу зосереджено на програмі пільгових кредитів «Доступні кредити 5-7-9%», яка стала основним інструментом фінансової підтримки малого бізнесу в Україні.

У статті розглянуті передумови виникнення альтернативного фінансування, які узагальнено представлено групою технологічних та економічних факторів. У статті визначено та проаналізовано основні переваги peer-to-peer позик порівняно з банківським кредитуванням, у тому числі: вища доступність та швидкість отримання позики; зниження значимості кредитного рейтингу; фінансове забезпечення соціально-значимих проектів; вища дохідність для інвесторів тощо.

Ключові слова: кредитування, мікропідприємства, малий бізнес, альтернативне фінансування бізнесу, місцевий бюджет, бюджет, податки.

Introduction

Statement of the problem. The full-scale war caused by Russia's invasion of Ukraine has led to irreversible changes, namely: significant losses were suffered by domestic businesses, especially in frontline regions and regions that were occupied and liberated from occupation, there was a sharp decline in employment and, accordingly, an increase in unemployment (official and actual – 30-40% of workers lost their jobs), and, above all, the normal flow of life for its citizens was disrupted. It should also be noted that there was high inflation (the consumer price index rose by 26.6% in 2022 and by almost 6% in 2023) and, as a result, a significant decline in real wages and real household incomes.

It should be noted that full-scale aggression has been the most destructive factor for domestic business. For example, in the first year of the invasion, businesses in Ukraine suffered significant losses, estimated at \$13 billion.

The full-scale war also had a negative impact on the activities of micro-enterprises, namely: the occupation of part of Ukraine's territory, the mass emigration of Ukrainians abroad, and changes in demand priorities led to a physical reduction in the number of micro-enterprises, the temporary suspension of their activities, and an increase in financial losses, for which the state did not create the necessary conditions to cover them.

It should be noted that small business is one of the most effective tools for stimulating local economic development. After all, it is a path to self-employment and job creation, as well as the formation of sources of income. Since small businesses are often family-owned, this makes it possible to involve household

members in them. Also, by paying taxes to the local budget, small businesses increase the budgetary and financial capacity of local governments. And by understanding the issues of local economic development and knowing the needs of consumers, the development of small businesses improves the quality of life of the local population.

In wartime, support for small businesses is extremely important. Small and medium-sized enterprises make up a significant part of the Ukrainian economy, providing jobs and tax revenues. Stable business operations are an important tool and component of Ukraine's economic security.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. The issues of lending and financing business needs in wartime have not been sufficiently addressed. In particular, the problems of activating bank lending in martial law conditions are studied by O. Dzyublyuk, I. Prikhn, and I. Chastokolenko. The peculiarities of bank lending and means of stabilizing financial support for business in Ukraine in wartime are covered in the works of Yu. Shushkov, Ye. Parfeniuk, and R. Turba. State programs to support business in wartime are analyzed by I. Khymych, T. Vynnyk, and N. Tymoshik. The problems of lending to microenterprises in Ukraine in conditions of economic crisis have been studied by such scholars as N. Versal, A. Zavoronok, M. Lapishko, N. Pogorelenko, O. Ruda, M. Turchik, O. Stupnitsky, and others. Among the researchers studying the problem of alternative financing, the following can be noted: F. Allen, E. Carletti, J. Qian, P. Valenzuela, S. Barnes, S. Moenninghoff (S. Moenninghoff), A. Wieandt (A. Wieandt), J. D. Roth (J. D. Roth), B. Zhang (B. Zhang), P. Baeck (P. Baeck), L. Collins (L. Collins).

However, despite numerous scientific developments in the field of analyzing lending and financing business needs, the issue of lending to small businesses in wartime requires more detailed research, as this will allow identifying key trends, patterns, problems, and ways to solve them.

The purpose of this article is to study small business lending in Ukraine in wartime, identify the main trends, patterns, and problems in small business lending, and explore innovative approaches to attracting credit resources and forming strategies to stimulate lending to domestic small businesses.

Results

One of the key ways for small and micro businesses to attract borrowed resources is through lending. In today's conditions, the need to support and develop domestic small businesses has become even more relevant, as the collapse of large enterprises poses a threat to the security of the domestic economy, and the creation of a favorable climate for economic recovery, even in conditions of loss, is a consequence of support for small businesses.

In Ukraine, small and medium-sized businesses are financed primarily through the reinvestment of their own profits, savings, funds from relatives and friends, and by obtaining loans, in particular from banks. SMEs also use consumer loans, as the mechanism for obtaining them is much simpler. However, despite the existing system of financial support, SMEs face significant difficulties in attracting credit funds. Several factors on both the demand and supply sides influence the restrictions on lending to domestic SMEs. In particular, in the current business environment in Ukraine, a bank-centric model of SME financing has developed, in which banking institutions play the leading role (Table 1).

Therefore, when analyzing the essence and problems of financial support for the banking sector in Ukraine, it should be noted that in the current economic conditions, the banking sector is the driving force of the domestic economy, and for this reason, the foundations of its financial support system have been laid.

Table 1.

Problems of small businesses accessing finance

Problems with access to financing					
Regulatory framework	Access to bank financing	Access to stock markets	Early stages of financing	Guarantee system	Professional development
Central bank independence Requirements for guarantees and collateral Creditworthiness information services	Competition in the banking system Scope of the banking sector Domestic loans to the private sector	Low capitalization of the stock market	Microfinance mechanism	Credit guarantee system Mutual guarantee schemes	Financial literacy Training for SME entities

Source: compiled from [1, 2, 3].

A fairly common situation for businesses is a significant deterioration in the economic situation of a small company that has taken out a bank loan. This may be caused not only by the terms of the loan, but also by various unforeseen circumstances, such as changes in the macroeconomic situation, actions of competitors, the weak position of the company in the local market, a sharp drop in demand for products, etc., accompanied by the need to repay the borrowed funds to the bank. Therefore, in the current environment, banks assess the risks of lending to small entrepreneurs as extremely high, which require compensation through higher interest rates, negatively affecting the dynamics of lending volumes in the SME sector. Thus, banks lack both incentives to attract small businesses and confidence in this customer segment. On the other hand, there are small businesses that need affordable credit resources but cannot obtain them due to high interest rates and, as a rule, do not trust banking structures that dominate the credit services market and are capable of unilaterally changing lending terms. In this regard, an important direction for intensifying cooperation between the banking and business sectors is institutional forms of doing business based on the principle of cooperation [4].

According to the State Statistics Service, micro-enterprises are the largest group of enterprises in Ukraine, as, in addition to legal entities of various organizational forms with up to 10 employees, they include thousands of individual entrepreneurs. As of January 1, 2022, there were 304,650 microenterprises and 1,585,000 individual entrepreneurs, employing 3,127,000 people, or 35% of the total number of people employed in Ukrainian enterprises [5]. This shows that domestic microenterprises, by attracting a significant number of the economically active population, ensure the well-being of millions of people and local communities, whose economies are based on micro business.

In recent years, given the current conditions, Ukraine has been making significant efforts to attract investment and stimulate business. For example, the Order of the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine “On Approval of Criteria for Determining Enterprises, Institutions, and Organizations of Importance to the National Economy” is an important document aimed at regulating and clarifying the criteria for determining key participants in the economic process. First of all, the order defines the criteria that will be used to identify important enterprises, institutions, and organizations [6]. This order contains criteria for determining the benefits and support provided to businesses, namely: simplified access to credit, support in the form of subsidies or grants, or other forms of state support. It should be noted that the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine has also launched a pilot project to provide financial support to startups on a competitive basis, particularly in the field of information technology. The initiative aims to stimulate an innovative approach and the development of innovative projects in the country [7].

This project provides funding for infrastructure development, training, and support for technological initiatives. This step will help increase the competitiveness of Ukrainian startups in the international market

and contribute to the country's economic growth. The Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine also adopted a resolution on granting business grants to support entrepreneurship in the country. The initiative aims to stimulate economic growth and provide financial support to various business sectors, including innovative startups. The resolution establishes procedures and criteria for obtaining grants, as well as mechanisms for monitoring their use [8].

It should be noted that the full-scale invasion by the Russian Federation has significantly worsened the situation with non-performing loans in the banking sector (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Share of non-performing loans in the banking sector, 2018-2024.

Source: based on [9].

The data in Figure 1 show that the main factor behind the decline in the share of non-performing loans in 2018–2021 was an increase in the volume of banks' loan portfolios and the removal of financially insolvent banks from the market. At the same time, since 2022, there has been a trend toward a significant increase in the share of such loans, indicating an increased risk of non-repayment. This process is driven by both macroeconomic factors and organizational challenges, including the mass closure of bank branches, disruption of operations due to regular air raid alerts and rocket attacks, and power shortages, which have significantly hampered the functioning of businesses under martial law.

Based on surveys conducted by the National Bank of Ukraine, small enterprises, including micro-enterprises, had a negative assessment of their financial situation even before the start of the full-scale war. Starting in the second quarter of 2022, the assessment of the current financial and economic situation was extremely negative (especially compared to medium and large enterprises), which probably had a negative impact on the terms of bank lending to microenterprises. At the same time, it is worth noting a certain paradox. The deterioration of the financial and economic situation of micro-enterprises as a result of hostilities did not negatively affect respondents' assessment of lending conditions. Otherwise, for small enterprises lending conditions improved, but the volume of lending decreased [10].

In order to increase the maturity of bank lending and improve credit conditions for Ukrainian businesses, the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine proposed the state program “Affordable Loans 5-7-9,” which, with the help of partner banks, aims to stimulate lending to the real sector of the economy and achieve the goals of developing entrepreneurship, in particular micro businesses. However, in practice, the maturity of loans under the program does not differ from bank loans, since the maximum term for an investment loan is 5 years, and for a loan to replenish working capital – 3 years [11]. Thus, the “Affordable Loans 5-7-9%” program has become the main instrument of financial support for small businesses in Ukraine (Fig. 2).

The significant growth in the volume of loans provided under the “Affordable Loans 5-7-9%” program is a sign of business interest in attracting credit resources and the objective value of these resources thanks to state support. A positive factor is the maintenance of the growth rate of these loans in 2023 despite the development of a full-scale war in Ukraine.

Overall, the state program has played a positive role in providing credit support for the development of Ukrainian business both during the coronavirus pandemic and under martial law. After all, it is not only the low interest rate that deserves attention, but also the level of loan coverage by a state guarantee amounting to 50% of the debt.

Fig. 2. Results of lending to Ukrainian businesses under the “Affordable Loans 5-7-9%” program in 2020-2024.

Source: based on [12].

In 2023, the Cabinet of Ministers changed the terms of business lending under the 5-7-9% program. The 5-7-9 program establishes special conditions for business support aimed at reducing financial risks and stimulating the development of small and medium-sized enterprises. Under this program, enterprises are given the opportunity to obtain loans on favorable terms: at an interest rate of 5% to 9% per annum and for a term of up to 10 years. This approach helps to attract additional financial resources for business development, reduce financial pressure, and increase the competitiveness of enterprises in the market. The program also provides additional support and advice to participants, contributing to their successful development [13].

During the war, there were many changes in the credit system, but the first stage of change was preferential loans, where the leaders in providing credit resources changed somewhat before and after the war (Table 2).

Table 2.

Share and number of preferential loans provided by banks

The name of the bank	Before 24.02.2022		After 24.02.2022	
	%	Number	%	Number
JSC PrivatBank	-38,09	-13265	56,19	5441
JSC State Savings Bank of Ukraine	-12,35	-4299	15,00	1453
JSC Raiffeisen Bank	-9,85	-3431	6,52	631
PJSC AB Ukrgasbank	-6,55	-2282	7,42	719
JSC Fuib	-5,92	-2060	3,26	316
JSC “ProCredit Bank”	-5,53	-1925	3,02	292
JSC Kredobank	-4,14	-1443	0,72	70
JSC Credit Agricole Bank	-3,43	-1193	1,35	131
JSC OTP Bank	-2,10	-731	0,8	77
JSC Ukreximbank	-1,81	-630	1,35	131
Share of all other banks combined	-10,23	-3563	4,37	423

Source: based on [12, 14].

The data in Table 2 show that Privat Bank alone accounted for a significant increase in state-owned banks, with its share of new loans rising from 38.1% before the war to over 56.2% during the war. The share

of banks with foreign capital decreased by 30%; for example, the share of Raiffeisen Bank decreased from almost 10% to 6.5%, and that of ProCredit Bank from 5.5% to 3%. The share of banks with private capital almost halved: at PUMB, it fell from 5.9% to 3.3%, and at other banks, from 10.2% to 4.4%. Thus, the leaders in providing preferential loans were JSC CB PrivatBank, JSC State Savings Bank of Ukraine, and JSC Raiffeisen Bank, which had a significant market share. After February 24, 2022, there has been a change in the leaders of the preferential lending market. PrivatBank JSC and State Savings Bank of Ukraine JSC strengthened their positions, increasing their shares from 38.09% to 56.19% and from 12.35% to 15%, respectively, which indicates their dominant position in the market. It is also worth noting that other banks that previously had a significant market share, such as Raiffeisen Bank, PJSC Ukrgasbank, and JSC First Ukrainian International Bank, lost their positions, reducing their shares after the full-scale invasion.

In the context of analyzing micro business lending in Ukraine during martial law, it is worth paying attention to the maturity of loans. According to the National Bank of Ukraine, loans with a maturity of up to one year account for 68.5% of the microenterprise loan portfolio; loans with a maturity of one to five years account for 21.4%; and the share of loans with a term of more than 5 years is only 10.1% (for comparison, in the European Union, the maturity of loans for small businesses has the following structure: up to one year – 26%; from 1 to 5 years – 31%; more than 5 years – 43% [15]).

The results of the Small Business Sentiment Index survey conducted by the European Business Association as part of the Unlimit Ukraine project show that among the entrepreneurs surveyed, the majority, namely 80%, plan to attract funds to their businesses in 2024 (in 2023 – 67%), using their own funds (40%) and, to a lesser extent, grants (20%), loans (12%), and investments (9%).

For the most part, businesses rely on their own resources. The share of grant programs has decreased (20% compared to 21% in 2022), but intentions to take out loans (12% compared to 10% in 2022) and attract investment (9% compared to 6%) have increased. It should also be noted that most entrepreneurs cite low purchasing power, war and occupation of territories, economic decline and instability, rising prices for goods, resources and rent, corruption, as well as fiscal pressure and high taxes as the main obstacles to further development.

Lending is an important element of the economy that helps businesses grow. Traditionally, banks have been the main lenders in Ukraine, but alternative financing models have emerged to overcome credit constraints, including crowdfunding, peer-to-peer lending, venture capital, and microfinance, which are effective solutions, especially in difficult economic conditions, as they provide flexible, inclusive, and often accessible options for businesses to obtain financing. Using technology and innovative platforms, alternative financing allows for direct interaction between businesses and investors, bypassing traditional intermediaries and promoting democratization of access to capital.

Peer-to-peer lending, also known as peer-to-peer lending, involves a group of people coming together to lend money to each other without the involvement of banks. Ukraine was one of the first countries to legally recognize peer-to-peer lending, and this form of lending has since become more popular. Peer-to-peer lending has several advantages, namely: lower service costs; faster loan approval process; the ability to obtain a loan even if you do not have a credit history.

However, this form of lending also has its drawbacks, such as a high risk of loan default and no protection for borrowers in the event of borrower bankruptcy [17].

Crowd funding is an innovative and popular method of financing entrepreneurial activities. It allows you to use the capabilities of online platforms to pool small contributions from a large number of people to finance projects, startups, or social initiatives. This method bypasses traditional financing channels such as bank loans, venture capital, or government grants, facilitating access to capital and stimulating entrepreneurial innovation. Crowd funding can be classified into four main models: investment, charitable, reward-based, and loan-based, each of which serves different purposes and attracts different donors [18].

Grant programs from international organizations also play an important role in promoting the development of micro businesses around the world. These programs provide non-repayable financial support, allowing entrepreneurs to access the resources they need to start or expand their businesses,

implement innovative technologies, and enter new markets. Grant funding is extremely important for micro businesses, as they often face significant difficulties in obtaining traditional financing due to limited collateral, insufficient credit history, or increased risk perception on the part of lenders.

It should be noted that both grants and loans are popular support instruments that businesses actively use in wartime. However, these resources are often inaccessible to micro and small businesses for a number of reasons, namely: high interest rates on bank loans; lack of or insufficient collateral to secure loans; short term of use of credit resources, which is often insufficient to achieve the desired performance indicators for timely repayment of loan debt; a short period for a flawless credit history, which is one of the mandatory conditions for obtaining a loan, etc.

When considering sources of financing for small businesses, it is important to identify their advantages and disadvantages (Table 3).

Table 3.

Advantages and disadvantages of forms of financing for micro businesses in Ukraine

Forms of financing	Advantages	Disadvantages
Public funding	relatively inexpensive type of financing	long-term process of providing funds
Bank lending	a wide range of specialized banking products; the opportunity to obtain significant financial resources; long-term lending	high interest rates; difficulties in obtaining; long application processing time; decrease in the financial stability of the enterprise
Crowd funding	easy to obtain, free funding	used mainly at the startup stage
Grant funding	the possibility of obtaining a sufficient amount of funds for a long period; receiving funds on a non-repayable basis	high requirements of grantors for potential grantees; restrictions on grantees in independently choosing ways to use grant resources

Thus, the war in Ukraine has significantly affected the development of lending to micro, small, and medium-sized businesses. A significant portion of lending is directed toward supporting the population, businesses, and defense. The full-scale invasion has led to a reduction in business lending due to risks and instability. After the war ends, it will be important to encourage banks to provide loans to support the economic recovery of the country as whole and micro businesses in particular, as loans will be the driving force behind recovery and economic growth. In order to stimulate lending to micro businesses, it is necessary to develop and implement preferential lending programs for micro businesses, as well as programs for the reconstruction and support of affected areas and business entities.

Conclusions

It is important to improve lending legislation as much as possible, ensuring clarity and transparency of rules for all market participants, which will reduce risks and increase the confidence of both banks and customers. It is also important to establish an effective mechanism for regulating and supervising the activities of financial institutions, which will help to avoid unfair market practices and prevent excessive risks. Such measures will contribute to the creation of a stable environment for financial transactions and investments. In addition, it is necessary to actively work on developing financial literacy among businesses. Informed business borrowers will be able to make informed financial decisions and avoid debt repayment problems, which will help reduce insolvency and increase market stability. All these measures together can create favorable conditions for the development of the credit market in Ukraine.

A comprehensive strategy is needed to stimulate the development of alternative financial instruments in Ukraine. The first important step is to raise awareness among entrepreneurs about the advantages and mechanisms of alternative financing. This can be achieved through educational programs, seminars, and the dissemination of success stories that demonstrate the effectiveness of these models. Regulatory reform is equally important for creating a transparent and enabling environment for alternative financing platforms. This involves adopting legislation for crowd funding and peer-to-peer lending, as well as strengthening investor protection measures to build trust in these systems.

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